

NDAC/LO/091

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Standard coordinates for use in TYCHO astrometry

by L Lindegren

1. INTRODUCTION

The astrometric analysis of starmapper transits is facilitated by use of standard (plane or tangential) coordinates (x, y) for describing the coordinate direction of a star as function of time. This concept was introduced in NDAC/LO/090 for the double star analysis, and is here further elaborated for TYCHO astrometry.

2. STANDARD COORDINATES AND THE TANGENTIAL FRAME $[\underline{x}_t \quad \underline{y}_t \quad \underline{z}_t]$

For a given star, the astrometric analysis is generally confined to a small area (< 1 arcmin) around some *a priori* mean position. Let (α_t, δ_t) be some conventional, fixed point near the centre of that area and $\underline{z}_t$ the unit vector towards this point. With $\underline{n}$ denoting the unit vector towards $\delta = 90^\circ$, we define the *tangential frame* by means of the triad $[\underline{x}_t \quad \underline{y}_t \quad \underline{z}_t]$ with

$$\underline{x}_t = \langle \underline{n} \times \underline{z}_t \rangle, \quad \underline{y}_t = \underline{z}_t \times \underline{x}_t \quad (1)$$

This is a right-handed, inertial reference frame defined for any tangential point with $|\delta_t| \neq 90^\circ$. We may express the arbitrary coordinate direction $\underline{c}$ relative to this frame by means of the *standard coordinates* (x, y) :

$$\underline{c} = \langle \underline{x}_t x + \underline{y}_t y + \underline{z}_t \rangle = (\underline{x}_t x + \underline{y}_t y + \underline{z}_t) (1 + x^2 + y^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

where

$$x = (\underline{x}_t' \underline{c}) / (\underline{z}_t' \underline{c}), \quad y = (\underline{y}_t' \underline{c}) / (\underline{z}_t' \underline{c}) \quad (3)$$

Standard coordinates are uniquely defined by (3) as soon as $\underline{z}_t' \underline{c} > 0$, but of course they are mainly useful if $\underline{c}$ is close to $\underline{z}_t$, in which case

$|x|, |y| \ll 1$. In fact, we shall assume in the following that $(x^2 + y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sim 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (40") and that we aim at a *relative* accuracy in standard coordinates not worse than 10^{-4} , or an *absolute* accuracy better than 4 mas (worst case: generally we expect approximation errors < 1 mas). This permits several important simplifications in the treatment, e.g. that differential aberration within the 40" area can be neglected, as well as second-order terms in aberration, proper motion and parallax; that $\underline{z}'_t \underline{c} = 1$ to sufficient accuracy; and that the w and z directions as projected onto the tangential plane are practically orthogonal. With these approximations in mind we write (2)-(3)

$$\underline{c} = \underline{x}_t x + \underline{y}_t y + \underline{z}_t \quad (2')$$

$$x = \underline{x}_t' \underline{c}, \quad y = \underline{y}_t' \underline{c} \quad (3')$$

In equatorial coordinates, the components of the tangential triad are given by the 3x3 matrix

$$\underline{N}'[\underline{x}_t \quad \underline{y}_t \quad \underline{z}_t] = \begin{bmatrix} -s\alpha_t & -s\delta_t c\alpha_t & c\delta_t c\alpha_t \\ c\alpha_t & -s\delta_t s\alpha_t & c\delta_t s\alpha_t \\ 0 & c\delta_t & s\delta_t \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

3. VARIATION OF THE COORDINATE DIRECTION IN STANDARD COORDINATES

For a star with astrometric parameters $\alpha, \delta, \Pi, \mu_\alpha \cos \delta, \mu_\delta$ (referred to the epoch T_e) we may define a vector triad $[\underline{p} \quad \underline{q} \quad \underline{r}]$ with equatorial components

$$\underline{N}'[\underline{p} \quad \underline{q} \quad \underline{r}] = \begin{bmatrix} -s\alpha & -s\delta c\alpha & c\delta c\alpha \\ c\alpha & -s\delta s\alpha & c\delta s\alpha \\ 0 & c\delta & s\delta \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The coordinate direction at the arbitrary time T can then be written

$$\underline{c}(T) = \underline{r} + (\underline{p} \mu_\alpha \cos \delta + \underline{q} \mu_\delta)(T - T_e) - \underline{b}(T)\Pi/a_u \quad (6)$$

where $\underline{b}(T)$ is the barycentric ephemeris of the satellite and a_u the astronomical unit (radial velocity is neglected). Inserting (6) into (3') we obtain the standard coordinates on the simple form

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x(T) &= x_e + (T-T_e)\dot{x} + P_x \Pi \\ y(T) &= y_e + (T-T_e)\dot{y} + P_y \Pi \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

where

$$x_e = \underline{x}_t' \underline{r}, \quad y_e = \underline{y}_t' \underline{r} \quad (8a)$$

$$\dot{x} = \underline{x}_t' \underline{p} \mu_\alpha \cos \delta + \underline{x}_t' \underline{q} \mu_\delta, \quad \dot{y} = \underline{y}_t' \underline{p} \mu_\alpha \cos \delta + \underline{y}_t' \underline{q} \mu_\delta \quad (8b)$$

$$P_x = -\underline{x}_t' \underline{b}(T)/a_u, \quad P_y = -\underline{y}_t' \underline{b}(T)/a_u \quad (8c)$$

The five star constants x_e , y_e , Π , $\dot{x}$, $\dot{y}$ take the rôle of astrometric parameters in the least-squares determination being the central part of the TYCHO astrometry process. The advantage compared with the usual parameters $(\alpha, \delta, \Pi, \mu_\alpha \cos \delta, \mu_\delta)$ is that they will appear linearly in the observation equations, also for stars close to the celestial poles. The parallax factors P_x and P_y can of course be computed in advance for every transit, as soon as a convenient tangential point (α_t, δ_t) has been chosen. Having determined x_e , y_e , Π , $\dot{x}$, $\dot{y}$ by the least-squares process, we may recover the usual astrometric parameters by the following steps:

$$\begin{bmatrix} r_\ell \\ r_m \\ r_n \end{bmatrix} = \underline{N}' \underline{r} = \underline{N}' (\underline{x}_t x_e + \underline{y}_t y_e + \underline{z}_t \Pi) = \underline{N}' [\underline{x}_t \quad \underline{y}_t \quad \underline{z}_t] \begin{bmatrix} x_e \\ y_e \\ \Pi \end{bmatrix} \quad (9a)$$

$$\alpha = \text{atan2}(r_m, r_\ell), \quad \delta = \text{atan2}[r_n, (r_\ell^2 + r_m^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}] \Rightarrow \underline{p}, \underline{q} \quad (9b)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mu_\alpha \cos \delta &= \underline{x}_t' \underline{p} \dot{x} + \underline{y}_t' \underline{p} \dot{y} \\ \mu_\delta &= \underline{x}_t' \underline{q} \dot{x} + \underline{y}_t' \underline{q} \dot{y} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9c)$$

Note however that (9c) is not the exact inverse of (8b). It should be verified that (9c) is sufficiently accurate also close to the poles.

4. THE OBSERVATION EQUATION IN STANDARD COORDINATES

The observed quantity is the transit time τ_{obs} across a certain slit group. In terms of the quantity

$$u = w - w_{fg}^*(z) \quad (10)$$

(i.e. the distance from the group centre line in the direction of scanning) this is equivalently expressed by the equation $u_{\text{obs}} = 0$. From a given set of *a priori* astrometric parameters $\alpha_0, \delta_0, \Pi_0, \mu_{\alpha 0} \cos \delta_0, \mu_{\delta 0}$ (e.g. the TIC position), the known attitude and the known grid calibration $w_{fg}^*(z)$, we may compute an *a priori* transit time τ_0 . The difference between τ_{obs} and τ_0 is used to form the right-hand side of the observation equation. We prefer however to work in angular units rather than times, so we convert the time difference to a value for u at the observed transit time but corresponding to the *a priori* astrometric parameters:

$$u_0 = u_{\text{obs}} + (\tau_0 - \tau_{\text{obs}})\dot{u} = (\tau_0 - \tau_{\text{obs}})\dot{u} \quad (11)$$

where $\dot{u} = \dot{w} - \dot{z}t^*$ is the effective scanning speed. (This can be calculated from the attitude information, but possibly the nominal value 168.75 "/s is always sufficient.) Alternatively, u_0 can be calculated directly as the u -value at time τ_{obs} , according to the *a priori* astrometric parameters; this is of course more strict but perhaps less convenient. In any case, the observation equation for the transit becomes

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x_e} (x_e - x_{e0}) + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y_e} (y_e - y_{e0}) + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \Pi} (\Pi - \Pi_0) + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \dot{x}} (\dot{x} - \dot{x}_0) + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \dot{y}} (\dot{y} - \dot{y}_0) \approx -u_0 \quad (12)$$

if $x_{e0}, y_{e0}, \dot{x}_0, \dot{y}_0$ are the star constants corresponding to the *a priori* astrometric parameters. We shall now derive simple expressions for the partial derivatives in (12) by a process similar to eqns (20)-(22) in NDAC/LO/090, but with u replacing G .

Let $\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta w, \Delta z, \Delta c$ denote small variations in the standard and field coordinates and the coordinate direction, respectively. We have

$$\Delta u = \Delta w - t^* \Delta z \quad \left[\text{with } t^* \equiv \frac{d}{dz} w_{fg}^*(z) \approx 0 \text{ or } \pm 1 \right] \quad (13a)$$

$$\Delta w = \underline{w}'\Delta c (1 - \underline{c}'\underline{v}) = [\underline{x}_t' \underline{w} \Delta x + \underline{y}_t' \underline{w} \Delta y](1 - \underline{c}'\underline{v}) \quad (13b)$$

$$\Delta z = \underline{z}'\Delta c (1 - \underline{c}'\underline{v}) = [\underline{x}_t' \underline{z} \Delta x + \underline{y}_t' \underline{z} \Delta y](1 - \underline{c}'\underline{v}) \quad (13c)$$

whence

$$\Delta u = (1 - \underline{c}'\underline{v}) \left[(\underline{x}_t' \underline{w} - \underline{x}_t' \underline{z} t^*) \Delta x + (\underline{y}_t' \underline{w} - \underline{y}_t' \underline{z} t^*) \Delta y \right] \quad (14)$$

Here $\underline{v}$ is the barycentric velocity of the satellite, expressed in units of the light speed. The factor $(1 - \underline{c}'\underline{v})$ takes account of differential aberration.

Δx , Δy can be expressed in terms of Δx_e , Δy_e , $\Delta \Pi$, $\Delta \dot{x}$, $\Delta \dot{y}$ by differencing (7). Inserting into (14) we find the partial derivatives

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x_e} = (1 - \underline{c}'\underline{v})(\underline{x}_t' \underline{w} - \underline{x}_t' \underline{z} t^*), \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial \dot{x}} = (T - T_e) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x_e} \quad (15a)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y_e} = (1 - \underline{c}'\underline{v})(\underline{y}_t' \underline{w} - \underline{y}_t' \underline{z} t^*), \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial \dot{y}} = (T - T_e) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y_e} \quad (15b)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \Pi} = P_x \frac{\partial u}{\partial x_e} + P_y \frac{\partial u}{\partial y_e} \quad (15c)$$

It remains to express $[\underline{x}_t \ \underline{y}_t]'[\underline{w} \ \underline{z}]$ more conveniently in terms of the attitude and to make some further approximations.

5. THE ATTITUDE EXPRESSED IN THE TANGENTIAL FRAME

The attitude is defined as the celestial orientation of the telescope triad $\underline{Z} = [\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}]$, given e.g. by the 3×3 matrix $\underline{A} = \underline{N}'\underline{Z}$. Rotating $\underline{Z}$ by half the nominal basic angle about the third axis ($\underline{z}$), such that the first axis coincides with the viewing direction $\underline{f}$ (or $\underline{f}_f$, where $f = \pm 1$ is the field index), we obtain the triad

$$\underline{Z}\underline{A}_3(\frac{1}{2}f\gamma) = [\underline{f} \ \underline{w} \ \underline{z}] \quad (16)$$

where $\underline{w} = \underline{z} \times \underline{f}$ is the unit vector tangential to the scanning circle at the field centre. We note that the (proper) direction to the star, when observed on the starmapper, must be within about 0.0155 rad from $\underline{f}$, and the same can be said about the direction $\underline{z}_t$ to the adopted tangential point.

The transformation from the tangential frame to the optical frame (16) can be effected by the three rotations described by

$$\begin{aligned} [\underline{f} \quad \underline{w} \quad \underline{z}] &= [\underline{z}_t \quad \underline{x}_t \quad \underline{y}_t] A_1(\frac{1}{2}\pi - \theta) A_2(\zeta_t) A_3(-\eta_t) \\ &= [\underline{z}_t \quad \underline{x}_t \quad \underline{y}_t] \begin{bmatrix} c\zeta_t c\eta_t & c\zeta_t s\eta_t & s\zeta_t \\ -s\theta s\eta_t + c\theta s\zeta_t c\eta_t & s\theta c\eta_t + c\theta s\zeta_t s\eta_t & -c\theta c\zeta_t \\ -c\theta s\eta_t - s\theta s\zeta_t c\eta_t & c\theta c\eta_t - s\theta s\zeta_t s\eta_t & s\theta c\zeta_t \end{bmatrix} \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

From the first line of the transformation matrix we see that the field coordinates of $\underline{z}_t$ are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} w_t &= \underline{w}'\underline{z}_t = \cos \zeta_t \sin \eta_t \\ z_t &= \underline{z}'\underline{z}_t = \sin \zeta_t \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (18)$$

so that η_t, ζ_t are simply the field angles of the tangential point. From the third row we find that θ can be computed without using $\underline{w}$, viz

$$\theta = \text{atan2}(\underline{z}'\underline{y}_t, -\underline{z}'\underline{x}_t) \quad (19)$$

$\theta - \frac{1}{2}\pi$ is in fact the position angle of the projection of $\underline{z}$ onto the tangential plane. It follows that θ is *approximately* the position angle of the projection of $\underline{w}$. The exact position angle of $\underline{w}$ is obtained from the second row of the transformation matrix, viz

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_w &= \text{atan2}(\underline{w}'\underline{x}_t, \underline{w}'\underline{y}_t) \\ &= \text{atan2}(s\theta c\eta_t + c\theta s\zeta_t s\eta_t, c\theta c\eta_t - s\theta s\zeta_t s\eta_t) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The difference, or the non-orthogonality of the tangential projections of $\underline{z}$ and $\underline{w}$, amounts to

$$\theta_w - \theta = \arctan(\sin \zeta_t \tan \eta_t) = \arctan \frac{w_t z_t}{(1 - w_t^2 - z_t^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \approx w_t z_t \quad (21)$$

Given that (w_t, z_t) must be close to one of the slit groups, we find that

$$|\theta_w - \theta| \lesssim 5.6 \cdot 10^{-5} \approx 12'' \quad (22)$$

This is negligible to the required relative accuracy (10^{-4}). Neglecting also differential aberration (since $|\underline{v}| < 10^{-4}$) and second-order terms in w_t and z_t we have

$$[\underline{x}_t \quad \underline{y}_t]' [\underline{w} \quad \underline{z}] \approx \begin{bmatrix} \sin \theta & -\cos \theta \\ \cos \theta & \sin \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

and the partial derivatives

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x_e} \approx \sin \theta + t^* \cos \theta, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y_e} \approx \cos \theta - t^* \sin \theta \quad (24)$$